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1.0	01/07/2021	The Amendment to generate single-cell and single-nuclei data from endometriosis patients was approved on 26/07/2021 (AMD 874867-3). Thus, we will delay deliverable 4.1 to M30.
1.1	06/09/2021	Final revision

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DELIVERABLE 4.1

~1 mil scRNAseq for endometrium

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List of Acronyms

scRNA-seq	Single-cell RNA sequencing	snRNA-seq	Single-nuclei RNA sequencing	HCA	Human Cell Atlas
UMI	Unique Molecule Identifier	BMI	Body Mass Index	WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable	SNPs	Single Nucleotide polymorphisms	FDR	False Discovery Rate
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection	FACS	Fluorescence-activated cell sorting	QC	Quality Control

Purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to present the first version of the endometrial atlas across the lifespan. As part of Deliverable 4.1, we will be addressing two main areas:

- a) Mapping the healthy endometrium across the lifespan.
- b) Profiling changes in gene expression and cellular composition in the endometrium of women suffering from endometriosis.

The amendment describing the new areas for WP4.1 was approved on 26/07/2021 (AMD-874867-3). In the original version, we aimed to profile by single-cell genomics 40 full thickness uterine wall samples from (i) hysterectomies from living donors, and (ii) deceased transplant donors. As part of the new amendment, INCLIVA (Spain) will remain the only site collecting full thickness uteri, and the number of individuals recruited will be reduced to 20. The GRL-WSI partner (UK) will focus their activities profiling eutopic endometrium and ectopic endometriosis samples from endometriosis samples using single-cell genomics. The amended delivery deadline for WP4.1 was scheduled for July 21 (M19) but will now be June 2022 (M30). Therefore, by handing in this deliverable on September the 6th 2021 implies that would be updated later on.

In this document we will provide a description of the computational and experimental pipelines used to develop this project, as well as an overview of the samples profiled so far. In WP4.5 we will provide a description of the new cell states we define.

This document has been developed by GRL-WSI, which is the main lead partner of Deliverable D4.1 “1 mil scRNAseq for endometrium.”

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of the HUTER project is to create a reference atlas of the human uterus in health and disease. This project is aligned with the Human Cell Atlas (HCA) initiative which aims to profile all cells in the human body. In particular, this project is part of the “Reproductive Network”, an area of the HCA focused on profiling reproductive tissues. This document describes the experimental and computational pipelines developed as part of HUTER to generate an atlas of the human endometrium across the lifespan.

We have combined two protocols to profile fresh and frozen tissues. We have used single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) to profile cells from fresh and cryopreserved tissue, and single-nuclei RNA sequencing (snRNA-seq) to profile cells from frozen tissue. We have optimised protocols in both cases to obtain high-quality data. The advantage of snRNA-seq is the possibility to explore retrospective (frozen) sample collections. This is the case for the endometriosis samples we have used for this study.

The analysis of snRNA-seq data comes with its own challenges. The main challenge we observed is the cross-contamination by the “ambient RNA”, which is the pool of mRNA that have been released in the cell suspension during the nuclei isolation. As part of this project, we have developed a computational pipeline that corrects for ambient RNA contamination, improving the integration of snRNA-seq and scRNA-seq datasets. To integrate datasets, we have used Bayesian deep learning and variational inference approaches. These computational pipelines have proved useful to uncover novel cell states in previous human cell atlases, where experimental design, sample collection, and technical variability cannot be fully controlled.

Altogether, our experimental and computational analyses will allow us to generate a comprehensive single-cell atlas of the human endometrium across the lifespan.

1. INTRODUCTION

HUTER project

The HCA Initiative aims to generate a comprehensive reference catalogue of all human cells¹. Such an atlas must take into account the variability of cells in the human body, including inter-individual differences and changes associated with ageing. This is of particular relevance for reproductive tissues which are influenced by the regular fluctuations of hormones. To describe the dynamic features of a cell in an unbiased manner, the HCA relies on state-of-the-art single-cell and spatial genomics methods².

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The HUTER project is an European consortium aiming to profile the diversity of cells in the human uterus across the lifespan using single-cell genomics methods. The endometrium, the mucosal layer of the uterus, goes through cyclic phases of shedding, regeneration and differentiation which are active during the women's reproductive life. The two ovarian hormones, estrogen and progesterone, regulate the monthly cycles of endometrial growth. The main goal of Work Package 4 is to generate a reference atlas of the human endometrium.

The endometrium consists of two main layers: the basal layer, which remains attached to the myometrium in all stages of the menstrual cycle, and the functional layer, which is shed during menstruation. The basal layer is thought to be enriched in progenitor cells but their full diversity is yet to be explored. The majority of studies so far have been focused on profiling the functional layer, which can be biopsied without the need of surgery. In Deliverable D4.1, we will profile the endometrium from full thickness uterine wall samples from (i) hysterectomies from living donors, and (ii) deceased transplant donors.

In addition, we are also profiling the endometrium of endometriosis patients (amendment AMD-874867-3 approved on 26/07/2021) as part of WP4. Metadata collected for these donors include treatment, Body Mass Index (BMI), age of the donor and day of the menstrual cycle (amongst others). We will compare endometrium from healthy and disease conditions with the aim to describe changes in the endometrium of these patients, with important translational opportunities for the diagnosis and treatment of patients with endometriosis.

Endometriosis

Endometriosis is a common, chronic condition that has a significant impact on the quality of a woman's life. It is an endometrial pathology characterised by the growth of endometrium-like cells outside the uterus, including growth on the ovaries, fallopian tubes and peritoneum. Despite the high prevalence of endometriosis, affecting around 10% of women of reproductive age, non-invasive diagnostic tests and efficient treatments have not currently been developed. As part of HUTER, we seek to perform an atlas of endometrium from endometriosis patients that we will compare to our healthy uterine reference.

As described in WP3, we will profile between 20-80 endometrial biopsies from women with and without endometriosis using scRNA-seq and snRNA-seq. Our collection includes both eutopic endometrium and ectopic endometriosis tissue. This is a collaboration with Prof. Krina T. Zondervan and Dr. Christian Becker (clinician and researcher) (Oxford, UK). Ethics is in place to use samples for this work: ENDOX study (REC: 09/H0604/58), and FENOX study, REC: 17/SC/0664, 29/12/2017). We

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will profile both, fresh/cryopreserved samples using scRNA-seq methods, and frozen samples using snRNA-seq.

Single-cell vs single-nuclei profiling

Cells dissociated from fresh and cryopreserved specimens will be profiled by scRNA-seq while snRNA-seq is required to profile frozen tissues. Each of the protocols requires modifications for each tissue type. Frozen and cryopreserved protocols have the additional advantage of enabling multiplexing samples from different individuals, which can be further deconvoluted based on their genotype⁴. Multiplexing of individuals is an efficient way to reduce reagent costs and correct for batch effects.

SnRNA-seq poses experimental and computational challenges, and often requires dedicated customizations. For example, distinct tissues may require specific lysis buffers for nuclei extraction. Nuclei extraction is often associated with higher rates of ambient RNA. Ambient RNA is a confounder factor that has to be taken into account when analysing the data.

As described below, as part of HUTER we have generated novel experimental and computational pipelines to profile and integrate scRNA-seq and snRNA-seq data.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PIPELINE

Single-cell RNA sequencing

We have performed scRNA-seq on biopsies from (i) full thickness uterine wall samples, (ii) endometrium, and (iii) ectopic endometriosis tissue. As described in WP3, multiple sites were collected from the full thickness uterine wall samples, and those were used for multiple single-cell and spatial genomics methods. Endometrial samples were collected using the Pipelle® device. The Pipelle is moved up and down inside the uterus a few times and rotated 360 degrees to get the sample from the largest area possible. Endometriosis samples were either flash frozen for snRNA-seq or cryopreserved for scRNA-seq. For the latter, we optimised a protocol that preserves the transcriptional profile and cellular composition of the tissue. Briefly, upon collection the tissue is minced up, washed in ice-cold RPMI (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% (v/v) heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS; Gibco), centrifuged, and tissue pellet resuspended in CryoStor® cell cryopreservation media (Sigma-Aldrich) before freezing in the CoolCell™ cell freezing container (Corning) at -80°C.

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Tissue dissociation for all tissues was conducted in a two-step digestion protocol (Figure 1):

Step-1 Collagenase treatment (FT= Flow Through): Tissue was transferred to a sterile 10 mm² tissue culture dish and cut into <1 mm³ segments before being transferred to a 50 ml conical tube. Tissues were digested with 1 mg/ml collagenase type V in RPMI (Sigma-Aldrich), 0.1 mg/ml DNaseI (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% (v/v) heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS; Gibco) for 45 minutes at 37°C with intermittent shaking. Digested tissue was passed through a 40 µm filter, and cells collected by centrifugation (450×g for 5 minutes at 4°C). Cells were treated with 1X red blood cell (RBC) lysis buffer (eBioscience) for 5 minutes at room temperature and washed with 10x buffer (PBS containing 0.04% (v/v) BSA) prior to cell counting. Protocol available at: dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.76thren.

Step-2 Trypsin treatment (GF = Glandular Fraction): Pieces of tissue retained on the 40 µm filter were washed with PBS and further digested with Trypsin/EDTA 0.25% for 15 minutes at 37°C with intermittent shaking. Digested tissue was passed through a 40 µm filter, and cells collected by centrifugation (450×g for 5 minutes at 4°C). Cells were washed with flow buffer (PBS containing 5% (v/v) FBS and 2 mM EDTA) prior to cell counting. Protocol available at: dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.72dhqa6.

Figure 1. Tissue dissociation protocol. Endometrial Pipelle® biopsy is cut-up and digested using a two-step enzymatic dissociation protocol. Two cellular fractions per sample are yielded: flow-through (FT) containing all cells, and glandular fraction (GF): enriched for epithelial glandular cells.

Cells were loaded according to the manufacturer’s protocol for the Chromium Single Cell 3’ Kit v.3.1 to attain around 10,000 cells per donor. Libraries were sequenced, aiming at a minimum coverage of

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20,000 raw reads per cell, on the Illumina Novaseq 6000 systems; using the sequencing formats; read 1: 28 cycles; i7 index: 8 cycles, i5 index: 0 cycles; read 2: 91 cycles (3' Kit v.3).

Single-nuclei RNA sequencing (Pilot Study)

Single nuclei can be extracted from frozen samples following the steps highlighted in Figure 2A. Briefly, snap-frozen endometrial Pipelle® biopsy is cryosectioned at 50 µm thickness and 8 sections homogenised using the Dounce tissue homogeniser by 10-20 strokes of both pestle A and B. The homogenate is filtered through a 40 µm cell strainer and washed. The nuclei are then examined under the microscope. If a clean nuclei preparation is observed, the sample is further washed and loaded onto the 10X chip. If debris is present, the sample needs to be cleaned up further.

To determine which buffers work best to extract the nuclei from endometrial samples, we compared tissue homogenisation in: (i) buffer A, followed by washing in buffer B, and (ii) in homogenisation buffer, followed by washing in wash buffer. Please refer to Figure 2B and Table 1 for the composition of the different buffers used.

We observed that the nuclei preparation from endometrial samples contains a lot of debris and needs to be cleaned-up further to remove the debris and to reduce the amount of ambient RNA present. As highlighted in Figure 2C, we compared two approaches for clean-up: (i) using a Percoll gradient and (ii) nuclei sorting using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS). The Percoll gradient clean-up uses 90% Percoll solution (in PBS) and centrifugation at 20,000xg for 15 minutes at 4°C. For sorting using FACS, the nuclear stain DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) was used to visualise the nuclei and distinguish them from the debris during the sort.

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A) Typical nuclei extraction workflow

B) Testing different buffers for nuclei extraction

C) Testing different approaches for nuclei clean-up

Figure 2. Nuclei extraction pilot study. The typical workflow for nuclei extraction is shown in (A). Snap-frozen biopsies are cryosectioned, followed by homogenisation in the Dounce tissue homogeniser. The homogenate is then filtered and washed. The nuclei morphology is examined under the microscope and either directly loaded onto the 10X chip or cleaned-up further if debris is present. The buffers tested for extraction are shown in (B) and include tissue homogenisation in: (i) buffer A, followed by washing in buffer B, and (ii) in homogenisation buffer, followed by washing in wash buffer. (C) shows the approaches tested for nuclei clean-up using: (i) Percoll gradient or (ii) FACS prior to cell counting and loading onto the 10X chip.

Table 1: Buffer composition

Buffer A	Buffer B	Homogenisation buffer	Wash buffer
Sucrose (250 mM)	Sucrose (320 mM)	Sucrose (250 mM)	PBS (1x)
BSA (10 mg/ml)	BSA (10 mg/ml)	KCl (25 mM)	BSA (0.5%)
MgCl ₂ (5 mM)	CaCl ₂ (3 mM)	MgCl ₂ (5 mM)	RNaseIn Plus (0.2 U/µl)
H ₂ O - MilliQ	MgAC ₂ (0.1 mM)	Tris buffer (10 mM)	
RNaseIn (0.12U/µl)	Tris-HCl (10 mM)	Nuclease free water	
Supersasin (0.06 U/µl)	H ₂ O - MilliQ	DTT (1µM)	
Protease inhibitor (1x)	DTT (1 mM)	Protease inhibitor (1x)	
	Protease inhibitor (1x)	RNaseIN plus (0.4 U/µl)	
	RNaseIn (0.12U/µl)	Supersasin (0.2 U/µl)	
	Supersasin (0.06U /µl)	Triton X-100 (0.10%)	

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Single-nuclei RNA sequencing

The Amendment to generate single-cell and single-nuclei data from endometriosis patients was approved on 26/07/2021 (AMD-874867-3). The new deliverable deadline will be in June 2022 (M30), related to Tasks T4.2, T4.3, T4.4 and T4.5.

3. COMPUTATIONAL PIPELINE: ALIGNMENT & QC.

Alignment

For each sequenced library, we performed read alignment to the 10x Genomics reference genome, quantification and initial quality control (QC) using Cell Ranger Software using default parameters. Cell Ranger filtered count matrices were used for downstream analysis. In order to integrate our data with previous studies ⁵, we used CellRanger 3.1.0 and genome version GRCh38-3_0_0 for full thickness uterine wall samples. CellRanger v6.0.2 (genome GRCh38-2020-A) is thought to be better for snRNA-seq data, and thus, we utilised this tool to align the transcriptome from endometriosis samples, where both single-nuclei and single-cell transcriptomics data has been generated. Furthermore, we allowed Cell Ranger to include UMI detected from reads that align within intronic regions by enabling the preRNA option; this allows increasing the sequencing depth of nuclei, which are expected to contain a greater proportion of unspliced mRNA.

Donor deconvolution

Cells from multiple individuals were multiplexed under the same reactions for the endometriosis collection. In those cases, we demultiplexed samples using souporcell ⁴, which assigned single-cells into a number of groups that corresponded to the number of expected genotypes and that shared coherent sets of Single Nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) from transcriptomic reads. Souporcell produces a genomic variant file for each expected genotype, which it also uses to identify a number of cell doublets that contains a mixture of SNPs from different genotypes. To assign each individual to a phenotype, samples were genotyped using SNPs microarrays (genotype data not generated as part of HUTER). The correspondence of the genotypes was assessed by comparing the genotypic variant files produced from single cells and microarrays using the vcftools suite and selecting the assignment with the highest genotype similarity.

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Doublet detection, alignment of data across different batches and clustering

The 10X Genomics scRNA-seq data was analysed with Scanpy ⁶, with the pipeline largely following their recommended standard practices. In addition, we implemented a number of enhancements as described below.

Individual samples of single cell or single nuclei were initially analysed separately prior to be batch corrected into an integrated dataset, and had two-step diffusion doublet identification performed ^{7,8}. In short, the initial doublet scoring was performed with Scrublet ⁹ on a per-sample basis, with the scores diffused by overclustering the cells and reporting each cluster's median value. Doublets were identified from a distribution of these scores centred at the median and using an MAD-derived standard deviation estimate, with statistically significant cells after False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction flagged as doublets. The second diffusion step takes place in a joint multi-sample manifold, with the frequency of identified doublets in granular (Leiden resolution 10) clusters serving as the basis for the distribution and the statistical significance analysis being repeated. The only deviation from the implementation described in ⁸ is a greater stringency in calling doublets, using Bonferroni for FDR correction, and a significance threshold of 0.01. This doublet detection method was applied to all samples; however, additional cells were identified as doublets in the endometriosis samples that were demultiplexed by souporcell ⁴, which identified doublets based on the presence of multiple genotype variant features found in single droplets.

After filtering cell doublets, cells with a number of expressed genes below 500 and cells with more than 25% mitochondrial reads were also filtered and the samples integrated using scVI ¹⁰. We integrated the samples using either sampleID covariate or the individual deconvolved donor identities when samples were library pools with several genotypes. While the raw count matrices were used for the single-cell datasets, the expression of genes that were retrieved for single nuclei were denoised from ambient RNA prior to the manifold identification. For that task, decontX ¹¹ was used on each sample separately. We then excluded genes associated with cell stage progression by excluding all marker genes for G2/M and S phase that are listed inside the Seurat package ¹². The latent variables were used for neighbour identification, which is needed for Leiden clustering ¹³ and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) visualisation from the Scanpy package.

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QC: Single-cell RNA sequencing

So far, we have generated scRNA-seq data from the endometrium of 10 donors: 4 donors from the full thickness uterine wall study and 6 donors from the endometriosis study (125,382 cells). For the latter set of donors, the QC data for samples from the endometriosis cohort confirmed a good yield of high quality cells after processing these samples (Figure 3). Median mitochondrial is lower than 25% and the number of genes is higher than 1,500 in all cases.

Batch	Donor	Endometriosis	Treatment	Nb cells	Nb UMIs	Nb genes	% mito
1	ES345	No	FT	3773	7797	2499	8.60%
1	ES345	No	GF	3669	13405	3512	16.14%
1	ES345	No	FT	4574	8111	2500	9.03%
1	ES345	No	GF	3296	13193	3370	18.17%
2	FX1146	No	FT	14761	4902	2113	13.24%
2	FX1146	No	GF	11428	6705	2255	22.69%
2	FX1156	Yes	FT	9774	3889	1836	8.52%
2	FX9006	Yes	FT	13004	3660	1797	8.89%
2	FX1156	Yes	GF	1378	21928	4644	15.11%
2	FX9006	Yes	GF	292	21904	4962	15.91%
3	FX1156	Yes	FT	6179	5576	2104	15.55%
3	FX9006	Yes	FT	10626	4433	1742	14.66%
3	FX1156	Yes	GF	11816	3982	1072	22.47%
3	FX9006	Yes	GF	4598	5484	1902	17.43%
3	FX1125	Yes	FT	5686	12917	3840	9.44%
3	FX1176	Yes	FT	3036	11731	3794	7.53%
3	FX1125	Yes	GF	92	14057	3488	24.02%
3	FX1176	Yes	GF	1641	21956	4726	15.41%

Figure 3. Quality control metric for scRNAseq samples. List of samples and deconvolved donors that have been processed by downstream analysis. The median number (Nb) of UMI, genes or percent of mitochondrial (% mito) content is reported over the overlaid probability densities. FT = Flow Through (collagenase treatment) GF = Glandular Fraction (trypsin treatment).

QC: Pilot study nuclei

The pilot study done to benchmark the effect of experimental protocols on the quality of snRNA-seq data was designed to specifically compare two considered variations: the alternate use of the AB buffers versus the otherwise used homogenisation and wash buffers, and the use of cell sorting to remove potential RNA ambient contamination. To that aim, 2 pairs of samples that enable us to compare the two conditions within independent batches were produced. (see Figure 4).

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Donor	Batch	AB	Facs	Nb cells	Nb UMIs	Nb genes	% mito
FX1101	1	Yes	No	23816	4445	2561	1.19%
FX1101	1	No	No	24058	2881	1796	0.11%
FX1101	2	No	No	18927	4671	2638	0.07%
FX1101	2	No	Yes	21125	3078	1918	0.08%

Figure 4. Quality control metric for snRNA-seq samples. List of samples compared the benchmark nuclei extraction protocols. The median number (Nb) of UMI, genes or percent of mitochondrial (% mito) content is reported over the overlaid probability densities. AB = AB Buffer (instead of “default” buffers of homogenisation and wash); Facs = FACS sorting of nuclei.

In order to evaluate the amount of ambient RNA contamination that is found in the samples, we looked at the mean expression of immunoglobulin and hemoglobin genes, which are associated with plasma cells and erythrocytes and are the main source of ambient RNA contamination. However, the vast majority of such genes had no expression in all samples. The most outstanding observation was that the expression of one of the hemoglobin genes (HBB), was two fold higher in the Fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) sorted sample however, that only amounted to <5% of the nuclei with any HBB, so this is not conclusive.

Since no outstanding ambient RNA contamination could be detected using prior known contaminant markers, we quantified global ambient RNA contamination instead. In an analogous way to how decontX¹¹ identified ambient RNA to remove, we first compared the RNA composition found in 10X empty droplets to the RNA from any nuclei that Cellranger identified. This allows displaying, for any gene, the total fraction of its expression that is found in ambient RNA as opposed to nuclei (Figure 5).

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Figure 5: Estimated fraction of gene expression in ambient RNA. Fraction of UMIs associated with a given gene that is found in empty droplets as opposed to cells identified using the default cellranger pipeline. These fractions are displayed as a function of the number of cells in any given sample that had at least 1 UMI of the corresponding gene.

We used this estimated fraction to identify nuclei that contain larger amounts of ambient RNA, by computing the expectation of the fraction of the UMI a nucleus contains that originates from ambient RNA given the gene it expresses. To highlight potential cell-type dependency for the given amount of ambient RNA a nucleus might have, we used logistic projection to our endometrium reference⁵ (Figure 6). This strategy allowed us to render a crude prediction of cell-type amidst the different nature of scRNA and snRNA sequencing. The motivation behind the use of this cell type predictor is that it does not introduce a bias from the unsupervised clustering of cell types that would typically be prone to regrouping cells with similar QC metrics, which would be a confounding factor when the aim is to benchmark protocols and not to curate cell types. Within each sample, we note that the proportion of ambient RNA in a nucleus generally is high when its sequencing depth is low. The amount of ambient RNA is higher in the AB buffer when compared to the homogenisation and wash buffer, which is consistent with the slight increase of mitochondrial content that was previously noted (Figure 4). This result suggests the AB buffer generates more stress on the tissue. On the other hand, the amount of ambient RNA is slightly decreased in the FACS sorted sample.

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Figure 6. Fraction of ambient RNA in single nuclei. Fraction of UMIs predicted in single nuclei that is expected to originate from ambient RNA contribution. These fractions are displayed as a function of the number of UMIs and the color corresponds to the predicted cell type using logistic projection onto our endometrium reference ⁵.

The pilot experiment suggested against the use of the AB buffer that showed an increased amount of mitochondrial content and ambient RNA. On the other hand, the comparison done for benchmarking the use of FACS sorting vs Percoll clean-up is more nuanced, as the amount of ambient RNA was only slightly reduced. While a decreased amount of ambient RNA is desirable, the computational pipeline can minimize this contribution by denoising ambient RNA (using decontX for instance); on the other hand, FACS sorting individual samples is more likely to introduce an experimental confounding factor that is harder to correct.

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the pipeline, we denoised the count matrices using DecontX and performed scVI integration (see “computational pipeline” section). While the count matrices are denoised, a fair number of nuclei still have a significant sequencing depth which passes the QC threshold of 500 genes per cell (Figure 7). That included some low QC cells which tended to cluster together. As such, we considered supplementing the pipeline with a more stringent threshold of 2000 UMI per cell to filter low sequencing depth nuclei, which would be applied after the decontX denoising.

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Figure 7. Preliminary result using the computational pipeline: Umap and Leiden clustering obtained from snRNA-seq UMI count that are denoised using decontX. Highlighted clusters represent clusters that do not have specific cell type markers, as noted from extracting the best cell type markers using TD-Idf on the differentially expressed gene list detected by Wilcoxon test. A small cluster of 34 nuclei expressing typical cervical markers is also detected.

After applying the UMI threshold of 2000 UMI, the cell type composition of the individual samples is more comparable between them. The most outstanding observation is a slight decrease in the proportion of epithelial cells in the sample prepared using the AB buffers (Figure 8a). A large number of cells in all samples were undergoing cell division, which is consistent with the proliferative stage of the menstrual cycle this donor biopsy is from, and was used to evaluate the snRNA-seq protocols (Figure 8b).

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Figure 8. Curated snRNA cell types. a) Main manifold for single nuclei contains. The proportion of cell type listed in each sample is displayed in the colored bar plot B) UMAP coloured by cell cycle. C) the predicted cell type using logistic projection onto our endometrium reference ⁵.

Altogether, the above results show that retrospectively collected frozen endometrial biopsies can be used for snRNAseq and yield good quality nuclei. Moreover, the nuclei identity can be predicted robustly using logistic regression onto our endometrial reference.

With regards to choosing protocols for further sample processing, we will proceed with tissue homogenisation using the homogenisation and wash buffers, followed by a Percoll clean-up. This is based on the findings that buffers AB increase the amount of ambient RNA contamination, while FACS sorting does not significantly reduce the amount of ambient RNA contamination detected, but could introduce further experimental biases.

4. COMPUTATIONAL PIPELINE: ANNOTATION OF CLUSTERS.

Annotation of scRNA-seq datasets.

Identification, labelling and naming of the major cell types was done by manual inspection of marker genes and interpretation of these based on the literature. Marker genes are the genes differentially

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expressed across clusters using two approaches, where both evaluate the statistical significance of differences between cells belonging to a given cluster to all cells that do not.

For each cell, we estimated the cell cycle phase (G1, S or G2M) based on its expression of G2/M and S phase markers following the method described in ¹⁵ and implemented in ¹⁵ Scanpy score_genes_cell_cycle function. Briefly, the relative expression of these gene-sets was compared to the expression of a set of reference genes. Marker genes for G2/M and S phase were retrieved from the Seurat package.

After applying the QC filters described in the previous section and integrating data with scVI, we did observe that scRNA-seq samples from endometriosis patients were correctly integrated (Figure 9). We found the major cell types we will expect in this tissue: stromal, epithelial cells, immune cells, endothelial and perivascular cells. Cells were annotated using label transfer from our recent published study profiling the endometrium ⁵.

Figure 9. Curated scRNA celltypes. A) Main manifold for single cell data which contains 6 different genotypes that were integrated using scVI B) the predicted cell type using logistic projection onto our endometrium reference⁵.

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5. DATA DISSEMINATION

The computational tools developed as part of the HUTER project, are part of a recent publication led by HUTER postdoctoral fellow Louis-Francois Handfield:

“Mapping the temporal and spatial dynamics of the human endometrium *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Garcia-Alonso L, Handfield L-F, Roberts K, Nikolakopoulou K et al., biorxiv doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.01.02.425073> (accepted in Nature Genetics).

In addition, principal investigator Roser Vento-Tormo has presented HUTER data in multiple conferences listed below:

- 2021 Global health integrated organoid convening. Bill & Melinda Gates foundation.
- 2021 CTR Annual Meeting 2021. Placental-endometrial dialogue and pregnancy.
- 2021 Sanger Seminar Series.
- 2021 Single Cell Omics Germany
- 2021 10x SC-Spatial Webinar
- 2021 mini-symposium - Spatially resolved single-cell biology D-BSSE
- 2021 EMBL Conference: Visualizing Biological Data (VIZBI2021)
- 2021 Keystone Symposia Single Cell Biology
- 2021 Annual academic meeting: Royal College of Obstetrician & Gynaecologists
- 2020 Illumina Spatial Genomics and Transcriptomics Expert Panel.
- 2020 Single Cell Biology Conference, Wellcome Genome Campus.
- 2020 Single Cell and Spatial Transcriptomics, EMBL-EBI Industry Programme Workshop

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6. CONCLUSION

Deliverable D4.1 has two main goals:

- a) To generate a single-cell census of endometrium across the lifespan.
- b) To study changes of endometrium in women with endometriosis.

The COVID19 pandemic has affected the number of donors recruited on this project. To overcome delays in collecting endometrial tissue samples from full thickness uterine wall biopsies at the GRL-WSI, we have amended our proposal to profile endometrium from endometriosis patients. The amendment was approved on 26/07/2021 (AMD-874867-3).

Due to the shortage of samples, we have focused the first 18 months on optimising scRNA-seq and snRNA-seq protocols. As described in this report, we have successfully optimised both protocols, and have produced data for 7 donors in total. Based on our experience, we are confident we will be able to deliver the full dataset proposed by the end of this grant (M30, June 2022).

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Regev, A. *et al.* The Human Cell Atlas. *Elife* **6**, (2017).
2. Svensson, V., Vento-Tormo, R. & Teichmann, S. A. Exponential scaling of single-cell RNA-seq in the past decade. *Nat. Protoc.* **13**, 599–604 (2018).
3. Becker, C. M. *et al.* World Endometriosis Research Foundation Endometriosis Phenome and Biobanking Harmonisation Project: I. Surgical phenotype data collection in endometriosis research. *Fertil. Steril.* **102**, 1213–1222 (2014).
4. Heaton, H. *et al.* Souporecell: robust clustering of single-cell RNA-seq data by genotype without reference genotypes. *Nat. Methods* **17**, 615–620 (2020).
5. Garcia-Alonso, L. *et al.* Mapping the temporal and spatial dynamics of the human endometrium in vivo and in vitro. *Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory* 2021.01.02.425073 (2021) doi:10.1101/2021.01.02.425073.
6. Wolf, F. A., Angerer, P. & Theis, F. J. SCANPY: large-scale single-cell gene expression data analysis. *Genome Biol.* **19**, 15 (2018).
7. Pijuan-Sala, B. *et al.* A single-cell molecular map of mouse gastrulation and early organogenesis. *Nature* **566**, 490–495 (2019).
8. Popescu, D.-M. *et al.* Decoding human fetal liver haematopoiesis. *Nature* **574**, 365–371 (2019).
9. Wolock, S. L., Lopez, R. & Klein, A. M. Scrublet: Computational Identification of Cell Doublets in Single-Cell Transcriptomic Data. *Cell Syst* **8**, 281–291.e9 (2019).
10. Lopez, R., Regier, J., Cole, M. B., Jordan, M. I. & Yosef, N. Deep generative modeling for single-cell transcriptomics. *Nat. Methods* **15**, 1053–1058 (2018).

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11. Yang, S. *et al.* Decontamination of ambient RNA in single-cell RNA-seq with DecontX. *Genome Biol.* **21**, 57 (2020).
12. Butler, A., Hoffman, P., Smibert, P., Papalexi, E. & Satija, R. Integrating single-cell transcriptomic data across different conditions, technologies, and species. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **36**, 411–420 (2018).
13. Traag, V. A., Waltman, L. & van Eck, N. J. From Louvain to Leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Sci. Rep.* **9**, 5233 (2019).
14. Love, M. I., Huber, W. & Anders, S. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biol.* **15**, 550 (2014).
15. Tirosh, I. *et al.* Dissecting the multicellular ecosystem of metastatic melanoma by single-cell RNA-seq. *Science* **352**, 189–196 (2016).

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